

Research Papers

Nickel-cobalt spinel-based oxygen evolution electrode for zinc-air flow battery

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ABSTRACT

Zinc-air flow battery (ZAFB) represents a candidate for safe, cheap and non-toxic stationary energy storage, however, uneven zinc deposition and low efficiency of oxygen reactions on positive electrode still obstruct its commercialization. In our contribution, we address the latter challenge by performance enhancement of electrode for oxygen evolution reaction (OER) from highly alkaline electrolyte. This was achieved by applying a NiCo₂O₄ electro-catalytic layer onto the selected 3D nickel-based substrates via electrochemically-assisted deposition followed by calcination. The detailed physico-chemical characterization of the electrodes (specific surface area, conductivity, EDS, SEM + EDS, XRD) confirmed spinel structure of the prepared catalyst and its homogeneous deposition over the substrate. The electrochemical characterization of the electrodes was performed in three different set-ups using a complex methodology incl. voltammetry techniques, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, galvanostatic load and charge-discharge cycling in the developed 3-electrodes 3-compartments battery full-cell. For both Ni substrates the deposited NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer effectively lowered the OER overpotential due to significantly enlarged specific surface area. This effect was more pronounced for the foam substrate with more compact structure. The developed ZAFB with the optimized OER electrode achieved stable and efficient performance at high current densities of 100 mA cm⁻² (which is the highest reported one for cycling experiments) in a broad SoC range (0–80 %) with energy efficiency of 42.1 % and no decay of capacity utilization.

1. Introduction

Transition of the energy sector towards higher share of renewable sources represents part of global plans for carbon neutral energetics. However, renewable energy sources are mostly characterized by time-varying performance. Thus, for their optimal use, it is necessary to combine them with stationary energy storage of sufficient power and capacity, in order to increase the accessibility of energy from renewable sources by stabilizing and shifting the power curve in time. In recent years, the installed capacity of electrochemical storage has been increasing rapidly worldwide [1]. Due to their high longevity, robustness and operational safety, vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFBs) represent nowadays one of the promising solutions for large-scale energy storage. However, due to limited mineral resources, significant deployment of VRFBs is limited by the high acquisition cost [2].

Therefore, there is an intensive search for more investment-affordable energy storage alternatives. Zinc is an attractive metal for energy storage both in static and flow conditions, where flowing arrangement can extend durability of zinc battery [3]. Zinc-air flow battery (ZAFB), due to its non-toxicity, high availability of electrolyte precursors and thus lower investment costs, appears to be a suitable candidate for a stationary electrical energy storage [4]. Intensive research and development of the technology is currently taking place, including optimization of internal cell components [5], assembly of laboratory cells [6–8], and testing of semi-operational units on kW/kWh-scale [9]. However, ZAFB technology has not been commercialized yet, mainly due to its limited durability. The main limiting factors comprise: i) uneven deposition and dissolution of zinc (affecting both the stability and capacity of the system), ii) the sluggish kinetics of the positive electrode oxygen reactions limiting the energy efficiency of the system and iii) the limited chemical

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stability of the battery components in strongly alkaline electrolytes [10].

ZAFB utilize oxygen evolution reaction (OER) for charging and oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) for discharging at positive electrode, according to Eq. (1) (written in the charging direction).

This comes along with reduced battery size and costs per capacity, as in principle, for the positive half-cell, only caustic solution is needed for battery charge and atmospheric oxygen for its discharge. In reality, these advantages are accompanied with several challenges related to the need for catalyst utilization and more sophisticated construction of positive electrode (when compared, e.g., to std. RFB with only two, liquid and solid phases). ZAFBs cells can either use a single oxygen electrode with bi-functional catalyst for both OER and ORR or two separate electrodes dedicated to each reaction [11,12]. Bi-functional positive electrode is favourable from constructional point of view as it simplifies the construction of battery stack enabling a relatively simple bipolar arrangement. However, performance and stability of bi-functional catalyst is typically significantly lower when compared to the 3-electrode set-up, as it is hard to fulfil the requirements of the two different processes (transport of electrons and fluids, corrosion stability, catalytic activity) [3]. This also includes the choice of suitable supporting material for the electrode construction. The convectional ORR electrodes use carbon-based gas diffusion layer, typically containing hydrophobic polymeric binder, for securing that the air gets to the catalytic layer of electrode while the electrolyte does not penetrate through the electrode. These electrodes were adopted from hydrogen-oxygen fuel cell technology, where they are commonly used [11]. Unfortunately, carbon-based components are unstable at high potentials needed for oxygen evolution, which prevents the use of carbon-based gas diffusion electrode for OER [13]. Instead, nickel-based electrodes are typically employed for OER [14], which are known from alkaline water electrolysis [3]. Need for separation of OER and ORR electrodes, typically realized by porous diaphragm or separator, increases the complexity of the battery design, the overall ohmic resistance of the cell and requires the combined multi-cell battery stacks with monopolar (charging) and bipolar (discharging) electrode arrangement [11].

Nickel foam is the most widely used as ZAFB electrode material due to its sufficient stability under OER conditions (at highly alkaline pH, which is needed for high solubility of zincate ions) and relatively high surface area available for the reaction. Complex OER mechanism including 4-electron transfer is characterized by high activation energy barrier [15] which significantly limits the overall energy efficiency of ZAFB operation (same is true for hydrogen alkaline electrolyzers [16]). Therefore, researcher's interest is to find high performance and stable electrocatalyst for the reaction. The activation barrier for OER can be significantly decreased by several electrocatalysts, among those noble metal oxides, IrO₂ and RuO₂, are state of the art catalysts with the highest activity towards OER [17]. Despite their superior activity and sufficient stability, these catalysts are expensive. Since the ZAFBs are typically operated with alkaline electrolytes, some much cheaper, but still relatively stable alternatives can be used incl. Fe, Co and Ni based compounds [18]. The recent review on catalyst for OER in alkaline and neutral media provides overview of all possible catalysts [16]. The NiCo₂O₄ spinel catalyst has been reported in several publications as a suitable electrocatalyst for OER in zinc-air batteries [19–24]. While all these studies deals with the static type of the rechargeable zinc-air battery, so far only a single study has mentioned the behaviour of this promising catalyst as a part of bi-functional catalyst under electrolyte-flow conditions, i.e. in ZAFB [25].

To the best of our knowledge, our work presents the first systematic study of OER positive electrode development using NiCo₂O₄ spinel electrocatalyst for the charging reaction of ZAFB in 3-electrodes 3-compartment single-cell set-up. The study includes: i) optimization of electrode preparation by electrochemically assisted deposition of the

electrocatalyst on two different Ni-based substrates (mesh, foam) and subsequent calcination of the layer; ii) detailed physico-chemical characterization of the deposited catalysts prior and after the mid-term cell testing; and iii) complex electrochemical characterization of the prepared electrodes under well-defined conditions (temperature, current load) in non-flow and flow-through laboratory electrochemical cells. The mid-term stability of the electrodes was confirmed by flow electrolyser testing for up to 180 h. Experiments in the developed laboratory ZAFB are carried out in a broad range of SoC (0–80 % of the negative electrolyte), which is not common for ZAFB in literature.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparation of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode

For the preparation of catalytically activated electrodes, nickel foam (99 %, Inco Advanced Technology Materials Co., Ltd., thickness 1.7 mm, pore size 580 μm) and nickel mesh (95 %, Bibus Metals s.r.o, 0.9 mm thickness) substrates were selected and electrochemically-assisted deposition of the catalytic layer was used. The deposition solution consists of 1.813 g of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and 3.630 g Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O in 1 dm³ of demineralized water (DEMI, specific conductivity < 0.5 μS cm⁻¹). Prior to the deposition, substrates were pre-treated by sonication in ethanol for 2 × 0.5 h with change of ethanol between the cleanings. Deposition of the catalytic layer was performed in two-electrode arrangement with pre-treated substrate (geometrical surface 9 × 7 cm²) connected as cathode and IrO₂ activated Ti rod as anode. Deposition was done in a galvanostatic mode at a geometrical current density of 0.8 mA cm⁻² at 25 °C for 1.5 h. Substrate with the deposited Ni(OH)₂/Co(OH)₂ (as confirmed by our results of XRD analysis, data are not included within the manuscript) layer was subsequently rinsed in the demineralized water for several times to remove the residues of the deposition solution. The prepared samples were dried at ambient air for 12 h. After drying, the samples were calcinated in the air atmosphere at 325 °C for 4 h. Temperature rise during the calcination was 4 °C min⁻¹. During the calcination step, NiCo₂O₄ layer was formed on the Ni substrate. Catalyst loading was determined as a difference between mass of the bare Ni substrate and mass of the Ni substrate modified with the catalyst layer divided by the double geometrical area. Double value of geometrical area was used because of the simultaneous deposition of the catalyst layer on both sides of the Ni substrate. Catalyst loading was typically 1 mg NiCo₂O₄/cm². The following nickel-based OER electrodes were prepared and characterized: pristine nickel foam, pristine nickel mesh, catalytically activated nickel foam and catalytically activated nickel mesh.

2.2. Physio-chemical characterization of the NiCo₂O₄ powder

EDS analysis was performed using scanning electron microscope Hitachi FlexSEM 1000 equipped with Oxford EDS AZtecOne with XploreCompact 30 mm² detector. EDS analysis was performed at accelerating voltage of 15 kV. Specific surface area was determined by Brunauer-Emmett-Teller surface analysis (BET) based on the nitrogen adsorption with ASAP 2020. Electric conductivity was measured in a home-made cell consisting of two poly(vinyl chloride) tubes closed with copper pistons which were connected to the measuring cables. The cell was pressed with constant force of 20 cN m. Conductivity of the powder layer was measured by Solartron Analytical potentiostat SI 1287 and phase analyser Solartron Analytical SI 1260 in a current-less regime. Slope of the dependence of the resistance on the thickness of the layer (measured by micrometre) was used to calculate the electrical conductivity, following the formula $\sigma = \frac{1000}{a \cdot S}$, where σ represents the conductivity (S m⁻¹), a stands for slope of the dependence of the resistance on thickness of the catalyst layer (Ω mm⁻¹) and S is surface of the catalyst layer (7.89 mm²).

2.3. Electrochemical characterization in liquid electrolyte non-flow arrangement

Electrochemical characterization of the prepared OER electrodes in a non-flow electrolyte set-up was done in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH solution at 25 °C using three-electrode arrangement. The prepared electrode with geometrical area of 1 cm² was used as a working electrode, reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) was used as a reference electrode (all potentials within this section are thus related to RHE) and a nickel wire was used as a counter electrode (CE). Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was used to evaluate the ohmic resistance of the system. EIS was performed at frequencies 100 kHz–0.1 Hz with voltage amplitude of the perturbing signal 10 mV at 0 vs. RHE. Linear sweep voltammetry was used to measure OER polarization curves within a current density range 0–100 mA cm⁻² (with current sweep rate of 0.5 mA s⁻¹ cm⁻²). Tafel analysis of these curves was used to evaluate exchange current density, which represents the kinetic parameter of the OER and Tafel slope, which is connected with the rate-determination step.

EIS was used for comparison of the electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) of the tested samples (bare Ni mesh, bare Ni foam, NiCo₂O₄/Ni mesh, NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam, Ni sheet), according to [26]. EIS was performed at 1.5 V vs. RHE with maximal amplitude of perturbing signal 10 mV and frequency range of 100 kHz to 0.1 Hz. Simple equivalent electrical circuit consisting of serial connection of resistor and

constant phase element was used for parameters evaluation. Physical meaning of the resistor is the ohmic resistance of the measured system while physical meaning of the constant phase element corresponds to

the capacity of the double layer. The formula $C_{eff} = Q \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{1}{R_u} + \frac{1}{R_{CT}} \right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}}$ was used to convert the measured admittance to the capacitance. In the formula Q stands for admittance, R_u represents the ohmic resistance of the measured system, R_{CT} corresponds to the charge transfer resistance and n shows the similarity with the pure capacitor ranging between 0 and 1. Double layer capacity of the Ni sheet was used as a reference value for the calculation of the roughness factor following the formula $R_f = \frac{C_{dl, sample}}{C_{dl, Ni sheet}}$, where R_f represents the roughness factor, $C_{dl, sample}$ stands for the double layer capacity of the tested sample (F cm⁻²) and $C_{dl, Ni sheet}$ is the double layer capacity of the plain Ni sheet (F cm⁻²). [26] ECSA was determined as R_f multiplied by the geometrical area of the tested sample (1 cm²).

2.4. Construction of the flow cells

To suppress the instability of ZAFB due to the other electrodes (zinc and ORR electrode) the prepared OER electrodes were firstly tested in a laboratory flow electrolysis single-cell with hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) taking place at a pristine nickel mesh CE. The schematics of the

Fig. 1. a) Flow electrolysis cell for preliminary testing of OER electrode; b) schematics of testing apparatus for characterization of developed OER electrode in the electrolysis cell; c) developed 3-electrode 3-compartment ZAFB single-cell; and d) schematics of testing apparatus for characterization of developed OER electrode in ZAFB: 1) ZAFB cell; 2) electrolyte tank; 3) air gas cylinder; and 4) air pre-heating.

flow electrolysis cell is shown in Fig. 1a (construction derived from std. lab-cell by Pinflow energy storage, s.r.o.). It consists of aluminium end plates, nickel current collectors, elastomeric polyolefin-based flat gaskets, electrolyte distribution frames made of polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE), ion-exchange membrane Nafion N115 (Chemours) and polypropylene (PP)-based static mixers (SM). Prior to the cell assembly the membrane was pre-activated in different baths at 80 °C: 1 h in demineralized water, 30 min in H₂O₂, and 30 min in 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH bath. The geometric area of the electrodes was 20 cm². Flow-through distribution of electrolyte was used for both half-cell compartments, which were filled with PP-based SM to enhance the homogeneity of the electrolyte flow.

Fig. 1c shows a schematic of the developed ZAFB single-cell (construction derived from std. lab-cell by Pinflow energy storage, s.r.o.) in 3-electrodes 3-compartments set-up (i.e. using two separated positive electrodes and compartments for charging (OER) and discharging (ORR) reactions). Carbon-polymer composite plate PPG 86 (Eisenhuth) and graphite felt (provided by Pinflow energy storage, s.r.o., 20 cm² electrode area, compression ratio 25 %, thermally activated according to [27]) served as negative electrode. OER took place in the middle flow compartment, which was hydraulically separated from negative electrode compartment by anion-exchange membrane FAAM 20 (Fumatech) and from positive ORR compartment by porous PP-based separator (Celgard 5500 by Celgard). The membrane was first heat treated in air atmosphere for 20 min at 260 °C and then activated by soaking in 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH solution at 40 °C for 24 h, according to recommendation of the producer. ORR electrode consisted of a carbon paper-based gas diffusion layer (GDL BC 28, provided SGL) with the ink-spray deposited catalytic layer with commercial platinum-based electrocatalyst on carbon support (HiSPEC 4000 by Alfa Aesar, Pt loading of 0.5 mg cm⁻²) and PTFE binder (60 wt% in cat. layer, PTFE suspension Alglofen by Solvay). Carbon-polymer composite plate PPG 86 (Eisenhuth) with the milled serpentine flow field of 1 mm wide and deep channels served for the distribution of air within the ORR electrode. A lab-made electronic device was used to switch the electronic connection from the cell to the potentiostat between charging and discharging mode (see Fig. S1).

2.5. Electrochemical characterization in liquid electrolyte flow arrangement

The testing apparatus (see Fig. 1b) for the preliminary testing of the prepared OER electrodes under the electrolyte flow conditions consisted of a flow electrolysis cell, peristaltic pump (Watson Marlow), two separated electrolyte tanks and tubing connecting the tanks with the cell. Each tank contained 0.5 dm³ aqueous solution of 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH electrolyte. Evolving oxygen bubbles significantly increases overall resistance of battery and therefore it is desirable to remove bubbles effectively [11]. To enhance bubble removal and minimize effect of the electrolyte bubbling, the flow rate of electrolyte was set to 160 ml min⁻¹, i.e. double value with respect to the final testing in ZAFB single-cell. Mercury-mercury oxide reference electrode (MOE; Hg/HgO with potential of 0.098 V vs. NHE) was positioned on the outlet of the positive half-cell via a Luggin capillary. The whole testing apparatus was placed in a temperature-insulated box tempered at given temperature of 20 °C.

The prepared electrodes were characterized in a flow electrolysis cell by a procedure consisting of dynamic load curves and galvanostatic loads. A battery cyler BCS-815 (BioLogic) was used to accomplish this task. Load curve (LC) measurements were performed in the current density range of 0–100 mA cm⁻² with linear current density increase of 1.25 mA cm⁻² s⁻¹. Galvanostatic load was set on 50 mA cm⁻² for 6 h. Each repetition consisted of following steps LC and galvanostatic load. There were five repetitions followed by 125 min long pause at OCV for removing all the bubbles from the flow cell and from the electrolyte tanks, this is called series. There were five series (25 repetitions in sum) followed by a change of electrolyte and two more repetitions (6th series) were done (complete procedure is summed up in Table 1). Total time of

Table 1

Detail of the electrochemical characterization procedure in the flow electrolysis cell.

Series	Procedures	Number of repetitions
Series 1–5	Load curve (0–100 mA cm ⁻² , 1.25 mA cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	5× 5×
	Galvanostatic load (6 h, 50 mA cm ⁻²)	
	125 min at OCV for bubbles removal	1×
Series 6	Electrolyte exchange	1×
	Load curve (0–100 mA cm ⁻² , 1.25 mA cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	2× 1×
	Galvanostatic load (6 h, 50 mA cm ⁻²)	

the whole characterization was over 180 h.

From the load curves the following parameters were evaluated (for further description see Table 2): area specific resistance ASR (linear part of the load curve for a current density range of 15–50 mA cm⁻²), OER overpotential at 50 mA cm⁻² to theoretical OCP (η_{theo} , assuming theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE) of positive electrode under given conditions. The actual OCP was changing through 5 series, probably due to the electrolyte pH change, therefore the change of OCP (ΔOCP), change of actual overpotential (η_{act}) and pH change (ΔpH) were also evaluated.

2.6. Characterization procedure in alkaline zinc-air flow battery

Testing apparatus (see Fig. 1d) for characterization of the prepared OER electrodes in ZAFB consisted of a ZAFB single-cell cell (detail description in Section 2.4), peristaltic pump (Watson Marlow), mass flow meter (Omega), reference electrode MOE (Equilibrium) and a single electrolyte tank and tubing connecting tank with the cell. Technical air was preheated (by passing a 1 m long steel capillary submerged in the water bath tempered at 40 °C). The air was supplied to ORR electrode with a flow rate of 200 ml min⁻¹ controlled by the flow meter. Both negative and positive charging electrodes were supplied with a single electrolyte using the peristaltic pump, std. electrolyte flow rate of 80 ml min⁻¹. Electrolyte consisted of 0.7 mol dm⁻³ ZnO dissolved in 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH. The whole testing apparatus was placed in a temperature-insulated box tempered at a given temperature of 40 °C.

All the OER electrodes were tested in a zinc-air flow battery cell by a developed characterization protocol consisting of: EIS, dynamic load curves and combined galvanostatic-potentiostatic charge-discharge cycling. A potentiostat VSP-300 with 4 A booster (BioLogic) was used for the testing. Firstly, the battery was galvanostatically charged to theoretical 50 % SoC (with respect to zincate concentration in the electrolyte) using current density of 100 mA cm⁻². At this SoC EIS and load curves characterizations were performed. EIS was measured in OCV at potentiostatic mode in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 1 Hz with a

Table 2

Evaluated parameters (first 4 parameters evaluated from load curves measurements), the description of parameters, time frame of parameters acquiring.

Parameter	Description of evaluation	Sampling time
ASR	Areas specific resistance, linear part of load curve, evaluated from current density range 15–50 mA cm ⁻²	2nd series 1st repetition, 5th series 1st repetition, 6th series 2nd repetition
$\Delta\eta_{\text{theo}}$, s.2–5	Difference of OER overpotential (50 mA cm ⁻²) with respect to theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE	2nd series 1st repetition, 5th series 1st repetition
$\Delta\eta_{\text{act}}$	Difference of OER overpotential (50 mA cm ⁻²) with respect to actual OCP	2nd series 1st repetition, 5th series 1st repetition
$\Delta\eta_{\text{theo}}$, s.2–6	Difference of OER overpotential (50 mA cm ⁻²) with respect to theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE	2nd series 1st repetition, 6th series 2nd repetition
ΔOCP	Difference of measured OCPs	2nd series 1st repetition, 5th series 1st repetition
ΔpH	Difference of working electrolyte pH values	fresh working electrolyte and after 5th series

sinusoidal amplitude of 10 mV for both, charge and discharge mode of the battery. The load curve measurements for battery charging and discharging were performed in 0–200 mA cm⁻² current density range with linear increase of 5 mA cm⁻² s⁻¹. Subsequently, a galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling of the battery was performed at 100 mA cm⁻² in 0–80 % SoC range; charging was always terminated by the charge (80 % of theoretical capacity of zincate ions in the electrolyte), discharging cut-off voltage was 0.5 V (for galvanostatic discharging) followed by potentiostatic discharge at 0.5 V, until the current density dropped below 10 % of the charging current density (10 mA cm⁻²).

From EIS the charge $ASR_{\Omega,c}$ and discharge $ASR_{\Omega,d}$ area specific ohmic resistances were evaluated as a high-frequency intercept of Nyquist diagram with x-axis. The charge and discharge area specific resistances ($ASR_{tot,c}$, $ASR_{tot,d}$) of battery cell were evaluated from the slope of linear part of corresponding load curves (at the current density region of 50–200 mA cm⁻²).

2.7. Scanning electron microscopy and energy-dispersive spectroscopy

For the characterization of the OER electrode samples prior and after their battery testing, the scanning electron microscope (SEM) Hitachi S4700 was used in the secondary electron mode. Accelerating voltage of 15 kV and emission current of 10 μ A was used. Microscope Hitachi S4700 was equipped with SD (silicon drifted) detector of X-ray which enabled energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Lateral resolution of the detector is 1 μ m² with sensitivity of 10–100 ppm. Precision of measurement is up to 1 wt%. Accelerating voltage of 15 kV and emissive current of 20 μ A was used. EDS analysis was done in mapping of surface mode with 30 \times magnification and in mode surface analysis with 500 \times magnification.

2.8. X-ray diffraction analysis

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of the prepared OER samples was done with Co cathode that allows more precise determination of phases with presence of Ni. Spectra were measured from 2 $^{\circ}$ to 110 $^{\circ}$ (2 θ) with step 0.039 $^{\circ}$ (2 θ). Accelerating voltage of electron generator was 35 kV.

3. Results

The primary aim of this study was to decrease overpotential of the OER electrode in alkaline ZAFB. The result section is divided into the two parts. First one is focused on physico-chemical characterization of the self-prepared catalytically activated OER electrodes by electrochemically assisted deposition of a thin NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer onto the surface of nickel-based substrates (nickel foam and nickel mesh). Nickel substrates were selected due to the high stability and catalytic activity of the nickel for the OER from alkaline electrolytes. The selected commercially available substrates, i.e., mesh and the foam both have a reasonable ratio of available surface area to pores size to provide the sufficient surface area for the reaction and, at the same time, secure the efficient transport of ions towards and from the ORR electrode and back. The second part shows the results of electrochemical characterization of the electrodes in three different set-ups: i) batch experiments in static electrolyte, ii) performance and stability testing in flow electrolysis cell and iii) final electrode testing in 3-electrode 3-compartment ZAFB single-cell.

3.1. Physico-chemical characterization of the prepared OER electrode

3.1.1. Physico-chemical characterization of OER catalyst and electrode

Phase composition of the prepared catalytic layer was confirmed by XRD (see Fig. S2), which revealed the presence of the Ni phase, which is present due to the Ni mesh and NiCo₂O₄ phase. Synthesis of the NiCo₂O₄ catalyst was thus confirmed.

Composition of the NiCo₂O₄ catalyst was evaluated using EDS

method, which showed value of Ni:Co ration equal to 0.48 (27 at.% Ni, 56.4 at.% Co). This is in accordance with the expected value of 0.5 based on the stoichiometry ratio. BET surface area of the NiCo₂O₄ catalyst was determined as 69.5 m² g⁻¹ [28], which indicates that reasonable number of the active sites could be available. Electrical conductivity of the NiCo₂O₄ powder was 9.6 S m⁻¹, which represents sufficient conductivity in order to ensure an efficient three-phase boundary within the catalytic layer of the electrode.

3.1.2. SEM + EDS

Fig. 2 and Fig. S3 show comparison of SEM images of pristine nickel mesh (Fig. S3a) and the nickel mesh modified by NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer (Fig. 2a, b and Fig. S3b). The images illustrate that the catalytic layer is homogeneously deposited over the Ni substrate surface. Fig. 2a shows the presence of the cracks in the deposited layer, which were most probably formed during the calcination during the transformation of the Ni(OH)₂ and Co(OH)₂ precursors to NiCo₂O₄. As it is visible from the detail image of the catalytic layer (Fig. 2b), size of the catalyst particles is in order of units of micrometres. Fig. 2c, d shows comparison of the freshly prepared electrode and the electrode after stability testing. Comparison of the catalytic layers does not show significant changes in the morphology of the catalytic layer after testing.

Fig. S4 shows the results of EDS mapping of the Ni mesh modified with NiCo₂O₄ catalyst (NiCo₂O₄/Ni) surface. The distribution of the Ni, Co and O is shown in Fig. S4b–d, respectively. SEM-EDS images show predominantly homogeneous distribution of the catalytic layer, with exception of the small areas close to sharp edges, where the catalytic layer is being visibly peeled-off, most probably due to its worse adhesion to the substrate. Interestingly, oxygen distribution map (Fig. S4d) shows higher level of uniformity, which can be explained by the oxides present on the surface of the Ni mesh substrate.

The same analysis was done for the electrodes based on the Ni foam, as shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. S5. It is seen from the SEM analysis that the morphology of the catalytic layer is not affected by the substrate used. The catalytic layer distribution is homogeneous, which is also confirmed by EDS results shown in Fig. S6. Comparison of the SEM pictures of the freshly prepared electrode and electrode after testing shows small changes in the morphology as the layer is looser after tests. This is most probably caused by the oxygen evolution and flowing liquid electrolyte, which both have an effect on the morphology of the catalytic layer.

3.2. Electrochemical testing of the OER electrodes

This part of the results presents the complex electrochemical characterization of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrodes and their comparison with pristine nickel-based substrates, which was performed in three different set-ups.

3.2.1. Electrochemical characterization in non-flow arrangement

The polarization curves measured for all the tested electrodes under static electrolyte conditions are shown in Fig. 4a. These curves are internal resistance (IR) corrected based on the ohmic resistance evaluated from EIS measurements at a potential of working electrode of 0 V vs. RHE. From Fig. 4b it is clear that using pristine Ni mesh or Ni foam electrodes resulted in different shapes of the polarization curves. Ni foam substrate shows higher values of the overpotential at low current densities, however, from current densities above 15 mA cm⁻² the overpotential increase with increasing current density is lower compared to the Ni mesh. At the same time, the potential slope of both catalytically activated electrodes is much lower than for the pristine Ni electrodes.

Comparing the overpotential needed to reach current density of 10 mA cm⁻² (η_{10}) the lowest value was achieved for NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode (0.334 V) followed by NiCo₂O₄/Ni mesh with 0.346 V. On the other hand, the η_{10} values were 0.397 V and 0.440 V for pristine Ni mesh and Ni foam, respectively. This is obviously due to the effect of the

Fig. 2. Images from scanning electron microscope for: a) NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode, b) detail of NiCo₂O₄ particles, c) fresh NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode, d) used NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode.

catalytic layer deposited on the surface of the Ni substrate. Despite the substantial difference in surface areas of the Ni substrates (much larger in case of the foam), negligible difference in η_{10} value was observed between NiCo₂O₄/Ni mesh and NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam. Most probably it was due to the fact that the catalyst loading was the same for both Ni substrates (1 mg NiCo₂O₄ cm⁻²). As the OER is assumed to proceed preferably on the catalyst active sites, the reaction rates for both catalysed electrodes should be comparable. Another explanation can lie in the changed porosity of the Ni substrates. Due to the deposition of the catalytic layer within the Ni foam, the pores are getting smaller, which can reduce the available surface of the 3D electrode. This effect can be further enhanced by the evolution of oxygen bubbles and their trapping within the foam structure.

The potential slope of both pristine electrodes in the region (see Fig. 4a) is higher when compared to the catalytically activated electrodes. This observation can be explained by different wettability, affecting the adhesion of oxygen bubbles to the surface. It was observed by contact angle measurement that presence of the NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer increases the wettability of the electrode surface. Ni sheet with deposited NiCo₂O₄ layer showed strong hydrophilic nature with the contact angle below four degrees, which was actually below the measurability limit of the device used. Both catalysed electrodes provided much lower overpotential.

In order to gain deeper information of the properties of the tested electrodes, Tafel analysis of the measured polarization curves was done (see Fig. 4b and Table 3). Interestingly, in the case of the pristine Ni electrodes, up to three different Tafel slope regions were observed. Because the Tafel slope is related to the rate determination step of the electrochemical reaction, its value can be current density dependent as higher reaction rate can be connected with the change of the rate-determination step. It is also nicely seen from Fig. 4b that NiCo₂O₄/Ni

mesh electrode shows only one Tafel slope within the entire linear part of the Tafel curve, while NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode shows two Tafel slopes.

From Fig. 4b and Table 3 it is evident, that Tafel slopes increase with the current density. This is especially true for pristine Ni electrodes, which show three different linear parts of the Tafel curve. Values of the Tafel slopes higher than 120 mV dec⁻¹ can be, in some cases, explained by the effect of the active surface coverage by the adsorbents or intermediates, blocking thus the active surface. At the same time, Tafel slopes significantly higher than 120 mV dec⁻¹ can indicate issue with the Tafel analysis validity. Because of Tafel analysis represents simplification of the Butler-Volmer equation, one of the assumptions is represented by current density controlled exclusively by the kinetics of the electrochemical reaction. In the case of the Tafel slopes significantly higher than 120 mV dec⁻¹, the overall performance is probably not limited only by the kinetics of the reaction, but also by some another parameter. This can happen for example due to the excessive oxygen bubble formation at higher current densities and their slow removal from the electrode surface and internal structure of 3D electrode (particularly in case of the foam substrate).

When j_0 values are compared for pristine Ni electrodes and electrodes modified with NiCo₂O₄ layer for Tafel slopes below 120 mV dec⁻¹, the modified electrodes show higher values of the j_0 , i.e. higher kinetics of the OER.

The trend in catalytic activity of the tested electrodes corresponds to the evaluated ECSA values, which is in the order: NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam > NiCo₂O₄/Ni mesh > Ni foam > Ni mesh with ECSA values: 22,000; 5500; 83 and 51 cm². Two observations can be made based on the results: i) Ni foam offers more active sites when compared to Ni mesh (ECSA 83 and 51 cm² respectively) and ii) application of the NiCo₂O₄ catalyst layer increases ECSA value significantly for both Ni substrates

Fig. 3. Images from scanning electron microscope for: a) $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ foam electrode, b) detail of NiCo_2O_4 particles, c) fresh $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ foam electrode, d) used $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ foam electrode.

Fig. 4. a) Load curves and b) Tafel curves for pristine and catalytically activated Ni substrates at current density $0\text{--}100\text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ and geometric area of electrodes was 1 cm^2 . The potential is IR compensated. Pristine mesh (PM, yellow), catalysed mesh (CM, purple), pristine foam (PF, black) and catalysed foam (CF, blue). Working conditions: $0.1\text{ mol dm}^{-3}\text{ KOH}$, $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, RHE reference electrode, current scan rate of $0.5\text{ mA s}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-2}$. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(265 times and 107 times for Ni foam and Ni mesh substrate, respectively).

3.2.2. Electrochemical characterization in a flow electrolysis cell

The prepared OER electrodes were subsequently characterized in a flow electrolysis cell under the conditions more relevant to the final ZAFB application, i.e. using highly alkaline electrolyte and flow-through electrolyte distribution (cell and apparatus construction described in the Section 2.4). It is important to note that despite that electrolysis cell was used, it was operated far away from the standard conditions for alkaline water electrolysis, since $8\text{ mol dm}^{-3}\text{ KOH}$ electrolyte was used in our

system. Overall efficiency of this cell was not considered since our main focus was the OER process at positive half-cell. Thus, the full-cell parameters are not discussed in this section.

3.2.3. Mid-term characterization of the prepared OER electrodes

Within this section the initial and mid-term performance and stability of all four OER electrodes (2 pristine and 2 catalytically activated) is compared using ASR and overpotential η_{theo} at current density of 50 mA cm^{-2} evaluated from a complex electrochemical characterization under well-defined conditions (for approximately 180 h), as described in the Section 2.5.

Table 3

Overview of the electrochemical parameters of the oxygen evaluation reaction obtained from polarization curves and Tafel analysis.

Mark	Electrode	Tafel slope/mV dec ⁻¹	$j_0/\mu\text{A}$ cm ⁻²	η_{10}/V	$R^2/-$
1\$	Ni mesh	70	0.02	0.397	0.989
2\$	Ni mesh	186	89		0.984
3\$	Ni mesh	447	3320		0.987
1!	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /Ni mesh	67	0.07	0.346	0.997
1*	Ni foam	87	0.1	0.440	0.988
2*	Ni foam	193	59		0.998
3*	Ni foam	353	1298		0.995
1&	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /Ni foam	84	1.1	0.334	0.996
2&	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /Ni foam	145	94		0.996

In the Fig. 5a, the development of potential of studied OER electrodes is shown (measured vs. MOE) during the testing in a laboratory flow electrolysis cell. During the first galvanostatic load period, a gradual decrease of working electrode potential was observed for all four OER electrodes, most probably due to in situ cleaning and activation of the electrode surface under the oxidative OER conditions. The highest initial overpotential was exhibited by the pristine Ni mesh, followed by the pristine Ni foam. The rising potential slope of both pristine electrodes over the 5 series is, in absolute values, slightly more significant when compared to the catalytically activated electrodes. This could be explained by the observed differences in the electrode wettability due to the presence of the catalytic layer (discussed in more details in the Section 3.2.1), which may affect the oxygen bubble trapping within the electrodes structure.

As is visible from Fig. 5a, the potential of all four OER electrodes was gradually rising in time, which was probably due to gradual pH decrease of the working electrolyte caused by OER. Change of the electrolyte composition subsequently led to intensive net flux of water through membrane (for fluxes direction see Fig. 1c), approx. 80–100 ml (up to 20 % of initial volume) of electrolyte moved through the membrane towards CE via combination of osmotic and electroosmotic fluxes during all 5 series (approx. 160 h). The change of the electrolyte composition is represented by the pH change of working electrolyte, shown in Table 4, which summarizes selected parameters evaluated from the load curves including: change of the theoretical overpotential $\Delta\eta_{\text{theo, s.2-5}}$ (i.e. with respect to theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE, at current density 50 mA cm⁻², second column); change of the actual overpotential η_{act} (i.e. with respect to actual OCP, third column); change of actual OCP of the working electrode (fifth column) between initial value after system stabilization (1st repetition from series 2) and final value (1st repetition from series 5); change of $\Delta\eta_{\text{theo, s.2-6}}$ (at current density 50 mA cm⁻², fourth column) after initial stabilization and after electrolyte exchange; and change of pH (last column) between the beginning of experiment and the last repetition before electrolyte exchange. For the detailed parameters description, please see Table 2. Growth of η_{theo} between 2nd and 5th series was significant (see second column of Table 4). However, we can see that the corresponding change of $\Delta\eta_{\text{act}}$ remained almost constant, as the actual OCP of working electrolyte also increased due to pH decrease. Therefore, the observed increased η_{theo} are mostly affected by gradual change in electrolyte composition (for detailed discussion see supplementary section 1).

To evaluate the OER electrode under the initial conditions, both electrolytes were exchanged after 5th series (i.e. after 25 repetitions) and two more repetitions of the characterization procedure were performed. The fourth column of Table 4 shows the comparison of overpotential differences ($\Delta\eta_{\text{theo, s.2-6}}$), showing only a minor overpotentials increase when compared to the initial values. Interestingly, the overpotential of both pristine OER electrodes decreases in time after the exchange, which is in contrast with behaviour of the catalytically

activated electrodes. This phenomenon could be explained by the fact that the surface of pristine nickel is more sensitive to the surface oxidation than the catalytic layer and the concentration of active sites available for the reaction on the electrode surface changes in time and the longer time is needed to achieve steady state. These results confirm that the electrode potential increase was mostly affected by the change of pH of the working electrolyte. In the final application of the electrodes, ZAFB, the electrolyte composition change is much less significant, because the changes caused by OER during battery charging are reversibly compensated by the ORR during the battery discharge. Moreover, the use of a single electrolyte tank also suppresses the changes caused by electrolyte constituents permeation through the membrane.

Load curves of the OER electrodes constructed from the corresponding load curve measurements (after performance stabilization, i.e. 1st repetition from series 2) are compared in Fig. 5a. In agreement with the trend observed for galvanostatic load measurements, pristine Ni mesh exhibited the highest initial overpotential and ASR, while pristine Ni foam showed lower overpotential due to the larger available surface area, which agrees with the results of preliminary electrochemical testing in non-flow arrangement (Section 3.2.1). From the dynamic load curves measurements, performance of both catalytically activated Ni electrodes seems to be almost the same, while from steady state galvanostatic load measurement we observed slightly lower polarization for the catalytically activated Ni foam. This could indicate different oxygen bubble effect under dynamic and constant polarization when compared to NiCo₂O₄ catalyst deposited on the Ni mesh and Ni foam, respectively.

Shape of the load curves in the activation region (approx. 0–10 mA cm⁻²) indicates that the mechanism of the OER on the Ni electrode is changed due to the presence of the catalytic layer — a short plateau appearing at 0–10 mA cm⁻² most probably originates from the surface oxidation of the spinel catalytic layer. In general, the application of the catalytic layer significantly decreases overpotential and ASR for OER for both substrate materials: η_{theo} at 50 mA cm⁻² of the electrode with deposited catalytic layer decreased in case of Ni foam substrate by 0.05 V (14 % of the value for pristine electrode) and for Ni mesh substrate by 0.09 V (23 %). Comparison of OER electrodes performance (after initial stabilization (I), last series before electrolyte exchange (A) and after electrolyte exchange (E)) for mesh-based electrodes is represented by load curves in Fig. 5b (only nickel mesh electrode shown for better orientation, all parameter changes are summarized in Table 4). For both pristine and catalysed electrodes, the shape of the load curves got back to the initial ones after the electrolyte exchange, which correlates with the results from galvanostatic loads and confirms promising stability of the developed electrodes.

Catalysed nickel mesh and nickel foam electrodes were characterized after the mid-term stability test by SEM, the resulting images are compared with the initial ones in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 (in c and d for both mentioned figures). After mid-term stability test, most of the catalytic layer remained at the surface of the nickel substrate. In case of Ni mesh, the presence of more cracks on the electrode surface suggests minor degradation of the catalytic layer. Despite this observation, both catalysed electrodes showed very stable performance within the 180 h of continuous galvanostatic operation at relatively high current density.

3.2.4. Characterization of OER electrodes in ZAFB single-cell

As shown in Fig. 1c, the final design of our zinc-air flow battery is a 3-electrode set-up, which consists of three separate cell compartments. Within the negative electrode compartment the graphite felt electrode is located, which serves as substrate for zinc deposition during the battery charging. The OER electrode is located in the middle compartment with independent electrolyte distribution, which is hydraulically separated from the negative electrode compartment by anion exchange membrane. The electronic connection to OER electrode is realized via Ni frame. Third compartment accommodates the gas diffusion electrode for the ORR and it is separated from the middle compartment by micro-

(caption on next page)

Fig. 5. a) Evolution of OER electrode potential within the mid-term stability experiment for the four Ni-based electrodes: pristine mesh (PM, yellow), catalysed mesh (CM, purple), pristine foam (PF, black) and catalysed foam (CF, blue). b) Initial load curves of the four tested OER electrodes taken from the 1st repetition of series 2; c) Load curves for PM and CM electrodes. d) Comparison of ASR (left bar) and η_{theo} (right bar, lighter color) evaluated from dynamic load curves. I — after initial stabilization (2nd series, 1st repetition), A — last series before electrolyte exchange (5th series 1st repetition), E — after electrolyte exchange (6th series 2nd repetition). Experimental conditions: electrolyte 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH, electrolyte flow rate 160 ml min⁻¹, 20 °C, constant load for 6 h at 50 mA cm⁻², load curve measurements (0–100 mA cm⁻², 1.25 mA cm⁻² s⁻¹), 5 series (each consists of 5 repetitions) and 2 more repetition after electrolyte change. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 4

Comparison of parameters change at different stages of experiment evaluated from load curve measurements shown in Fig. 5.

OER electrode	$\Delta\eta_{\text{theo., s.2-5}}/\text{mV}$ at 50 mA cm ⁻²	$\Delta\eta_{\text{act.}}/\text{mV}$ at 50 mA cm ⁻²	$\Delta\eta_{\text{theo., s.2-6}}/\text{mV}$ at 50 mA cm ⁻²	$\Delta\text{OCP}/\text{mV}$	$\Delta\text{pH}/-$
Details of comparison	Between series 2 and 5	Between series 2 and 5	Between series 2 and 6	Between series 2 and 5	Between series 1 and 5
Pristine mesh	82	24	14	58	-1.08
Catalysed mesh	75	23	21	44	-1.00
Pristine foam	69	36	3	62	-1.10
Catalysed foam	59	10	18	50	-1.06

porous separator. Both membrane and separator are partially permeable for the electrolyte. The oxygen bubbles evolving during the battery charging decrease the effective cross-section area, increasing internal battery resistance. Moreover, they can be trapped within the OER electrode structure, which is difficult to be recovered. The probability of this phenomenon was expected to be higher for nickel foam due to its larger internal porosity and larger surface area. From this point of view, the use of nickel mesh was anticipated to exhibit lower clogging by bubbles and shadowing of ORR electrode.

All four OER electrodes were tested in the final design of our ZAFB single-cell, to evaluate the electrodes performance under the real

application conditions incl. the shadowing effect of different electrode matrixes (mesh vs. foam). At first, it is important to mention that during the OER electrodes development, we have modified our ZAFB single-cell construction from the planar substrate to 3D carbon felt substrate negative electrode, which significantly increased the performance and durability of the battery, when compared to the planar substrate. Thus, the previous targeted current density (50 mA cm⁻²), which was also used for long term galvanostatic load test in the flow electrolysis arrangement, was increased to 100 mA cm⁻² in the final design of ZAFB single-cell.

The comparison of EIS spectra and load curves measured in 50 %

Fig. 6. a) EIS spectra (C — charge connection, D — discharge connection), b) charging and discharging dynamic load curves and c) discharging load curves and power curves of Zn-air battery single-cell for the four tested Ni-based OER electrodes at 50 % SOC (with respect to the electrolyte composition); LC-load curve, PC-power curve; d) Development of efficiencies (EE — energy efficiency, CE — coulombic efficiency) and capacity utilization (CU — capacity utilization) of during galvanostatic-potentiostatic cycling at 100 mA cm⁻²; General conditions: 40 °C, 80 ml min⁻¹ electrolytes flow rate (0.7 mol dm⁻³ ZnO dissolved in 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH), 200 ml min⁻¹ air flow (technical, preheated to 40 °C). PM — pristine mesh, CM — catalysed mesh, PF — pristine foam, CF — catalysed foam.

SOC (according to zincate concentration in the electrolyte) at the beginning of battery testing is shown in Fig. 6c, the evaluated parameters are summarized in Table 5. The cell ohmic resistance evaluated from the high frequency region of the EIS spectrum was around $1.2\text{--}1.3\ \Omega\ \text{cm}^2$ for charging and $1.5\text{--}1.65\ \Omega\ \text{cm}^2$ for discharging for all 4 cells. Generally higher ASRs for discharge connection is as expected since the ORR electrode is placed behind OER electrode, see Fig. 1c, thus the inter-electrode distance is larger for discharging cell connection. Ohmic ASR difference between catalysed and pristine electrode from EIS measurements is rather insignificant.

Comparison of the load curves (Fig. 6a) shows significant differences of the cell polarization during battery charging: the cells with the catalysed Ni electrode showed significantly lower overvoltage (by about $200\ \text{mV}$ at $100\ \text{mA}\ \text{cm}^{-2}$) due to the reduced activation polarization of the positive electrode. Interestingly, the decrease of the linear part slope of the load curve for catalysed electrodes compared to the pristine electrodes is observed for both charge and discharge part of ZAFB (see ASR_{tot} in Table 5). In the other words, the use of catalysed electrodes for OER had also positive effect on the discharging process (see Fig. 6a, b). Since the ASR_{Ω} values for catalysed electrodes are not significantly lower, the decrease of the $ASR_{\text{tot-d}}$ is probably caused by the different surface properties of the catalytic layers which may affect the removal of oxygen bubbles from OER electrode generated during the preceding charging load curve (complete bubble removal takes tens of minutes, see effect of pause between the galvanostatic loads in Fig. 5a). Hypothesis of the catalytic layer affecting bubble removal is also supported by a slow bending of the discharge load curves in the region of high current densities for cell with the pristine foam electrode, which implies limitation of mass transfer (in terms of products removal).

Fig. 6d shows the trends in cell efficiency and capacity utilization for combined galvanostatic-potentiostatic cycling at $100\ \text{mA}\ \text{cm}^{-2}$ within 0–80 % SOC range (galvanostatic charging, discharge with voltage hold at 0.5 V). The averaged evaluated parameters over 20 cycles are summarized in Table 5. From the results it is clear that the pristine nickel OER electrodes exhibit mutually comparable cell parameters (EE of 32–33 %), and the application of the Co–Ni spinel catalytic layer increased the voltaic efficiency by about 3 % for Ni mesh substrate and even by 10 % for the Ni foam substrate. Coulombic efficiencies for all four cells were around 95 %, with slightly lower values for the pristine Ni foam, which was most probably related to the poorer performance of the positive ORR (discharging) electrode. No decrease in the capacity utilization or cell short circuit was observed during std. short-term experiments (approx. 3 days) nor for longer testing. The stable CU was achieved mainly due to the fact that a single electrolyte was used for both negative and charging positive electrode, and thus, no capacity loss was possible due to the permeation of electrolyte active species (i.e., zincate ions) through the membrane to the other electrolyte. Despite the observed decay of VE within the cycling (due to gradual deterioration of ORR electrode as discussed elsewhere), the performance stability of the cell was sufficient to provide stable charge-discharge behaviour for the combined cycling protocol used incl. galvanostatic discharge with potentiostatic holds. The initial energy efficiency of charge-discharge cycle was over 40 % for both catalysed OER electrodes, which is rather high for a battery using an oxygen-based positive half-cell and is clearly attributed to the enlarged surface area of the electrodes due to

the catalyst layer deposition. The observed gradual decrease in voltage and therefore energy efficiency was caused by the increasing polarization of the cell during discharge, probably due to the gradual flooding of the positive ORR (discharge) electrode by electrolyte permeating through the separator from the OER compartment. The hydrophobicity optimization of the catalytic layer of ORR electrode by optimized content of PTFE binder is currently proceeding within our research team and its results are expected to be included within our next publication.

As mentioned in the beginning of this section, it was expected that the nickel foam will cause large shadowing effect to the ORR electrode (when compared to Ni mesh substrate) resulting in higher ohmic ASR of the discharging cell. Nevertheless, if we compare ohmic and total resistance for the discharge part of the cell for the catalysed electrodes, we can see that both values are in fact lower for the nickel foam. Within this study always new ORR electrode with identical composition was used and the cell internal construction thus differs only in OER electrode. Possible explanation of the lower $ASR_{\text{tot-d}}$ is that the foam with lower permeability for electrolyte served as better protection against flooding of the ORR electrode when compared to mesh with more open structure. This theory is also supported by the evolution of energy efficiency during the cycling (see Fig. 6d). Energy efficiency of the cells with Ni foam electrodes are relatively stable over 20 cycles, on the other hand, relatively fast decay of energy efficiency (almost 10 %) is clearly visible in case of Ni mesh electrodes. From these observations we can conclude that although the foam-based electrodes have higher shadowing effect on the ohmic ASR in the discharge connection, their more compact structure has overall positive effect on the discharge performance of the single-cell. Moreover, it is crucial to pay attention to the homogeneous distribution of the electrolyte flow within the ZAFB to secure effective removal of the evolving oxygen bubbles and to prevent the generation of gas bubbles pockets trapped within the OER compartment, which can further decrease the homogeneity of electrolyte distribution within the electrode.

3.2.5. Comparison of the achieved results with literature

The measured OCV of the battery in 50 % SOC for discharging was approx. 1.5 V and the cell with catalysed Ni foam OER electrode achieved relatively high maximum power density of $150\ \text{mW}\ \text{cm}^{-2}$ at $40\ ^\circ\text{C}$. The value is lower when compared to the highest reported peak power density of $270\ \text{mW}\ \text{cm}^{-2}$ for zinc-oxygen flow battery [6], but the mentioned study uses pure oxygen (we used air) and, moreover, their oxygen electrodes active area was 2.5 times larger than the zinc electrode one due to the asymmetric cell arrangement used (current and power densities were calculated with respect to the geometric area of zinc electrode). These conditions significantly influence the polarization of positive electrodes that has major effect on the battery performance. However, the reported voltage efficiency at room temperature at $100\ \text{mA}\ \text{cm}^{-2}$ is around 50 %, which is comparable to our study (44.4 % at $40\ ^\circ\text{C}$), taking into account the mentioned differences in cell geometry.

Kherzi et al. [29] for their tubular ZAFB single-cell reported the power peak density of $75\ \text{mW}\ \text{cm}^{-2}$ and the voltage gap (difference between charging and discharging voltage plateau) of 0.84 V at $60\ \text{mA}\ \text{cm}^{-2}$ (our study 0.93 V at $50\ \text{mA}\ \text{cm}^{-2}$), although also here the larger positive electrode area was used due to the tubular cell arrangement. Pichler et al. [25] reported the use of the NiCo_2O_4 ($10\ \text{mg}\ \text{cm}^{-2}$ loading)

Table 5

Zn-air battery single-cell parameters for the four tested nickel-based OER electrodes; $40\ ^\circ\text{C}$, $80\ \text{ml}\ \text{min}^{-1}$ electrolytes flow rate ($0.7\ \text{mol}\ \text{dm}^{-3}$ ZnO dissolved in $8\ \text{mol}\ \text{dm}^{-3}$ KOH), $200\ \text{ml}\ \text{min}^{-1}$ air flow rate (technical, preheating to $40\ ^\circ\text{C}$). ASR evaluated from the EIS and load curve measurements at 50 % SOC (in terms of neg. electrolyte). Efficiencies and capacity utilization averaged from the values for 1–20 cycle, presented in Fig. 6.

OER electrode	$ASR_{\Omega,c}/\Omega\ \text{cm}^2$	$ASR_{\Omega,d}/\Omega\ \text{cm}^2$	$ASR_{\text{tot},c}/\Omega\ \text{cm}^2$	$ASR_{\text{tot},d}/\Omega\ \text{cm}^2$	CE/%	VE/%	EE/%	CU/%
Pristine mesh	1.26	1.64	3.00	3.34	95.4	34.8	33.2	77
Catalysed mesh	1.28	1.64	2.50	3.02	95.4	37.5	35.8	77
Pristine foam	1.30	1.50	2.42	3.56	92.3	34.8	32.1	74
Catalysed foam	1.20	1.56	2.16	2.84	94.9	44.4	42.1	78

as a part of the mixture together with $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_3$ (25 mg cm^{-2}) as catalytic layer for bi-functional positive electrode in ZAFB. The recorded charging voltage at 50 mA cm^{-2} was approx. 1.95 V, i.e. slightly lower compared to our study (2.08 V at the same current density), but with 10 times higher catalyst loading. The overall performance of their battery is comparable to our system, reported voltage efficiency was 51 % at 50 mA cm^{-2} (ours is 44 % at 100 mA cm^{-2}). To conclude this section, the use of larger air electrodes or increased catalyst loading can further improve the performance of ZAFB cell, but the price of air electrode materials must be also considered.

Nonetheless, we demonstrate that our ZAFB single-cell of plane-parallel cell construction with Ni–Co catalytically activated OER electrode can be stably operated at high current density of 100 mA cm^{-2} (reasonable target for ZAFB based on [3]), moreover, in a broad SoC range of 0–80 %, with relatively high energy efficiency (42.1 %) and power density (150 mW cm^{-2}) and no capacity fade within the tested period. We believe that the achieved intensification of the ZAFB operation at low catalyst loading and high capacity utilization of the electrolyte is an important step towards the industrial application of the system for stationary energy storage within the ongoing energy transformation.

4. Conclusion

In this contribution we studied oxygen evolution reaction electrodes for alkaline zinc-air flow battery. At first, $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ electrodes were successfully prepared and characterized by a complex array of physico-chemical methods. Prepared electrodes were subsequently electrochemically tested in three different set-ups. Two set-ups were based on water electrolysis (under flow and non-flow conditions) to suppress zinc electrode instability. The final set-up employed the developed three-electrode, three-compartment zinc-air flow battery single-cell with carbon felt negative electrode for zinc deposition and discharging positive gas diffusion electrode for oxygen reduction. In a flow water electrolysis set-up, both catalysed OER electrodes show significant improvement of performance in terms of decreased overvoltage and area specific resistance. The performance of both catalytically activated electrodes was also confirmed stable within mid-term stability experiments (180 h testing for each electrode). Moreover, water management and pH control of the electrolytes was found to have significant influence on the OER electrodes performance.

The electrodes characterization in the zinc-air flow battery single-cell finally confirmed improved performance of both catalysed OER electrodes. Use of $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ catalyst efficiently decreased charging overvoltage by 200 mV and therefore increases the voltaic and energy efficiency up to 10 %, compared to the pristine electrodes. Interestingly, the nickel foam-based electrodes provided better performance and short-term stability, although they exhibited higher negative shadowing effect to ORR electrode, but in the same time they reduced the flooding rate of the ORR electrode by the electrolyte which extended the life-time of the battery. Mean energy efficiency of 42.1 % were achieved over 20 combine galvanostatic-potentiostatic cycles at 100 mA cm^{-2} for 0–80 % SoC range with no capacity utilization decay for alkaline zinc-air flow battery with $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ foam OER electrode. At 40 °C and 50 % SOC, this cell exhibited low ASR of 2.16 and 2.84 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for charging and discharging, respectively and relatively high discharging peak power density of 150 mW cm^{-2} .

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Přemysl Richtr: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jaromír Hnát:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jiří Charvát:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Martin Bureš:** Methodology. **Jaromír Poceďič:** Project administration, Methodology. **Martin Páidar:** Methodology. **Juraj Kosek:** Project administration.

Petr Mazúr: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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